

MATURATION OF FISH GAMETES IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE AFRICAN CATFISH (*CLARIAS GARIEPINUS*)

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Annotation. This study aimed to describe the early development of *Clarias gariepinus*, a species that has been introduced into various watersheds worldwide, in order to help the identification of its eggs, larvae and juveniles in natural environments. Newly fertilized eggs are spherical, with a double membrane, the density of which varies. Initially the larvae have little pigmentation but this intensifies during development. They have four pairs of well-developed barbells, an elongated body, long dorsal and anal fins, no adipose fin and vesicles surrounding the fin fold and barbells. The sequence of formation of the fins is: caudal, dorsal, anal, pectoral and pelvic. Growth pattern analysis revealed that metamorphosis usually occurs during the flexion stage. The reproductive performance of the species and its rapid early development favor aquaculture; however, they may also favor its invasion of natural environments, representing a threat for native populations [1].

Keywords: African catfish, invasive species, larvae, juvenile of fish, oogenesis.

Introduction

Most fishes have paired gonads, although one member of the pair may be consistently larger than the other in some species or only one gonad may be functional. Hagfishes and lampreys are unique in that only one ovary develops, from the fusion of two primordial in lampreys and from the loss of one ovary in hagfishes. Unlike sharks and other vertebrates, testes and ovaries in jawless fishes and bony fishes develop from only the cortex of the peritoneal epithelium, not from both the cortex and medulla.

Material and methods

Testes in immature males are typically reddish and take on a smooth texture and creamy-white coloration as the fish matures and spawning time approaches. The testes generally account for <5% of body weight (see below). Follicles within the testes produce the developing spermatoa through a series of meiotic and developmental transformations typical of vertebrates (spermatogonia, primary spermatocytes, secondary spermatocytes, spermatids,

metamorphosis, spermatozoa).

Fish sperm vary in size, shape, number of flagella (none to two), and presence or absence of acrosomes and other structures. Fish sperm are highly diagnostic of higher taxa and of some species. Sperm heads range in length from about 2 mm to 70 mm. The cap like acrosome at the anterior end of most primitive fish sperm is lost in practically all neopterygian fishes [2].

Oogenesis, the development of eggs, occurs within the ovary and also progresses through various stages involving oögonia, primary and secondary oocytes, and finally ova or eggs. Oögones develop from primordial sex cells in the germinal epithelium of the ovary wall. Proteinaceous yolk granules are deposited around primary oocytes during vitellogenesis, the precursors of yolk material being manufactured in the liver.

Oil droplets are incorporated in the yolk. Ripe eggs pass from the ovary through the oviduct, which is a continuation of the ovarian tissue, to the outside via the cloaca. In elasmobranchs, no direct connection between ovary and oviduct exists and hence eggs pass through the peritoneal cavity on their way to the oviduct. Egg resorption is a general process. Usually, most of the ripe eggs in an ovary are spawned while a small proportion is resorbed and the proteins, fats, and minerals contained in them are reused by the female for maintenance, growth, or production of more eggs. The number resorbed varies greatly among and within species, depending on fish size, number of previous spawning that season, and energy state of the female.

Most freshwater fishes and some coastal marine species diverge from this pattern and produce demersal eggs that are laid on the bottom. Many spawn in nests and engage in some form of parental care. Demersal eggs tend to be relatively large, up to 7 or 8 mm in salmon, anarhichadid wolf fishes, and zoarcid eelpouts. The largest teleost eggs are produced by mouth-brooding marine catfishes and range from 14 to 26 mm. Pigmented yolks produce colorful eggs in gar, catfishes, and salmon. The occurrence, number, and location of oil globules in the yolk differ among species. Oil globules may serve as nutrition for embryos, as flotation mechanisms, and, when pigmented with melanin, may help protect sensitive developing structures from harmful radiation[3].

Conclusion

Exceptions show the premium placed on assuring survival of young rather than just on producing large numbers of eggs. In mouth-brooding cichlids, fecundity increases in relation to the square of the length of the female because mouth size increases only linearly with increasing body length. Because of resumption,

fecundity estimates based on counts of ripe eggs may not necessarily indicate true fertility, which is the number of viable offspring produced. Fecundity estimates for live bearing fishes are further complicated by the consumption of eggs by developing embryos, a form of maternal provisioning.

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